

Getting to the root of the problem: Informing design through the exploration of the gardening experience of older women

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Abstract Gardening is a leisure activity that can be beneficial for both health and wellbeing of older women. Although the ageing process can provide more challenges for this group, adaptation of the activities and the tools will allow them to continue the beneficial activities. To explore the gardening experience of an older female (50+) target group and focus on their perception of the various different tasks, this online survey-based research included a range of different gardening tasks and the motivations for doing gardening activities. Participants (N=89) answered 38 questions regarding gardening motivation, experience and comparison of different tasks.

Moving heavy things in the garden is done by few of the older women and this task is more often done by their spouse/partner. It is also perceived as the least enjoyable and the most difficult gardening activity. Improving this task will empower older women to do this supporting task independently so that they do not rely on social networks or paid help. Tool aspects were found to be important for older women's gardening motivation, and improving on the task through product design is therefore expected to have a positive impact on gardening participation and consequently health and wellbeing of older women.

Keywords *Older women, Motivation to garden, Tool design, Healthy ageing*

Introduction

The population of the UK is ageing: it is projected that by 2039 over 24% of the UK population will be over 65 (Office for National Statistics, 2015). The older population is predominantly female (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2013), 2013). The health and wellbeing of the growing group of older women is one of the challenges facing product designers. According to ACSM (2007), regular physical activity, including aerobic activity and muscle-strengthening activity, is essential for healthy ageing.

Gardening is a popular leisure activity for older adults in the UK and older women in particular (Dunnett & Qasim, 2000; The Horticultural Trades Association, 2011). Park, Shoemaker, & Haub (2008) found that gardening can meet the recommendations for aerobic activity. It can also contribute to hand and body strength and flexibility (Park & Shoemaker, 2009), retaining attention span and memory abilities in persons with Alzheimer's type dementia (D'Andrea, Batavia, & Sasson, 2008), better self-reported scores on physical function, reduced bodily pain and improved hand function (Park, Shoemaker, & Haub, 2009), greater overall self-reported life satisfaction (Sommerfeld,

Waliczek, & Zajicek, 2010) and greater overall physical health (Everard, Lach, Fisher, & Baum, 2000).

Most gardening activities rely on the use of various gardening tools. Other studies have explored a variety of variables associated with the use of a range of tools (Brown Tebben & Thomas, 2004; e.g. Chang, Park, & Freivalds, 1999; Leppänen, Kallionpää, & Vilkki, 1998; Mirka, Jin, & Hoyle, 2009; Päivinen & Heinimaa, 2009; e.g. Tudor, 1996; Zinnecker, 2011). However, an overview of the act of gardening as a leisurely practice for older women and how the individual tasks of gardening contribute to the overall experience has not been made. To develop products that have a positive influence on older women's participation in healthy gardening activities, this overview is needed as it will provide focus on the most relevant areas of this experience.

Considering the above, there is a need to explore the gardening experience from the point of view of the target group in order to prioritise the improvement of relevant tasks and accompanying tools. Three areas of the experience have been identified and will be explored:

1. An overview of the reasons people do gardening in order to investigate their motivation.
2. The perception of importance of tool aspects to establish to what extent the tools and attributes of these tools affect the user.
3. A comparison of the tasks older women pursue and how they feel about the different gardening tasks to identify the tasks with the most potential for improvement.

The results will be compared to older men to enable the identification of relevant differences between the genders. The combination of these results creates a more complete overview of the gardening experience of female leisure gardeners over 50, which will inform the design for more suitable gardening tools for this group.

Methods

Research design

An online survey using Qualtrics online survey platform (2015) was developed to address the research objectives and was active during the summer of 2015. The survey consisted of 38 questions and was developed in an iterative process; pilot sessions were held with three volunteers of the target group and thereafter improvements to the method were implemented. The project was approved by Coventry University's ethics process and all participants provided informed consent.

The survey commences with an introductory sentence 'One of my reasons for gardening is ...' followed by

twenty potential reasons for gardening, including some generic leisure motivations based on Beard & Ragheb (1983), together with specific motivators relating to gardening and an open text field with 'other reason'. The participants rated each statement on a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) (Aitken, 1969) of 'not a reason' to 'an important reason'.

Participants were questioned using a VAS from 'no influence' to 'major influence' about the relative importance of tool related aspects versus other gardening related aspects on their motivation to undertake a gardening task.

Questions were included on which tasks people participate in, enjoy and find difficult. The latter two were posed on VAS from 'not enjoyable' to 'very enjoyable' and 'not hard' to 'very hard' respectively. For the tasks participants claimed not to do, follow-up questions were asked on their reasons for not doing the task.

Recruitment

The research aimed to approach leisure gardeners. Participants were approached through Royal Horticultural Society's The Garden magazine in July 2015 and a link to the survey was posted on a number of online gardening forums and tweeted by the RHS several times.

Participants

The participants were part of a larger study, which included 68 male and 142 female adults (18+) that currently live in the United Kingdom, do (some)

Table 1. Reasons for gardening for females and males over 50.

Reasons for gardening	Females over 50 (N=88)		Males over 50 (N=53)	
	Median	Range	Median	Range
It makes me happy	100	73	87	100
I feel in touch with nature	94	100	69	100
Influence how the garden looks	89	100	80	100
Relaxing	86	100	62	100
Feeling of accomplishment	85	100	84	100
The quiet and solitude	83.5	100	57	100
Getting some fresh air	83.5	100	59	100
Growing something out of nothing	72	100	65	100
Healthy exercise	71.5	100	58	100
Sense of ownership	52.5	100	37	100
Create nice environment to have friends round	43	100	47	100
Allows me to develop skills	39.5	100	20	100
It needs to be done	34.5	100	28	100
I like that I can control it	20.5	100	42	100
It gives me something to do	13	100	28	100
Sense of being in a garden community	2.5	100	0	99
Other reason	0	100	3	98
Partner/spouse wants me to do it	0	100	0	99
I do it to help someone else out	0	100	0	86
I am paid to do it	0	58	0	100

Medians on VAS of 'not a reason' (0) to 'an important reason' (100).

Median scores for influence of gardening experience related aspects

Figure 1. Median scores for gardening experience related aspects for females over 50 (N=83). Medians on VAS of 'no influence' (0) to 'major influence' (100).

gardening and have an outside space to grow plants. The data of all males (N=53) and females (N=89) of 50+ years old were extracted from this data.

Data analysis

The data was analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 22. Descriptive statistics were used to examine initial results. Normality tests and plots were applied to the various scale variables and showed lack of normality, thus non-parametric Mann-Whitney, Spearman's correlation and Pearson's chi-squared tests were applied.

Results

Reasons for gardening

Median scores were calculated for twenty statements on people's reasons for gardening separately for females and males over 50 (Table 1). 'Other' reason

entries related mainly to growing fruit and vegetables and providing a place for wildlife.

Importance of tool related aspects

Results show that for this group of females over 50, most tool related aspects are important with high median scores for suitability, ease of use and weight of the tool as well as tool handle comfort and quality of the tool (Figure 1).

Tasks: enjoyment and difficulty

Participants were asked to rate how hard and how enjoyable each of the gardening tasks was on a VAS scale from 'not hard at all' or 'don't enjoy it' to 'very hard' or 'enjoy it very much'. The hardest task was reported to be moving heavy objects, followed by trimming hedges and pruning trees (Table 2). The least enjoyable task was moving heavy objects (Table 3).

Figure 2. Scatterplot of hardness versus enjoyment of tasks for median values.

Figure 2 plots task difficulty against task enjoyment. The graph suggests a negative correlation between enjoyment and perceived difficulty and Spearman's correlation indicated a correlation of $r = -.670$ at $p = .017$.

Effect of gender

Mann-Whitney tests on significant differences in enjoyment of gardening tasks based on gender show only for weeding (median_{males} = 47, median_{females} = 54, $U = 1643$, $z = -2.63$, $p = 0.008$, $r = -0.22$) and pruning plants (median_{males} = 58, median_{females} = 67, $U = 1668$, $z = -2.11$, $p = 0.035$, $r = -0.18$), with women enjoying these tasks more than men. Gender based significant differences in how hard a task is could only be established for pruning trees (median_{males} = 12, median_{females} = 30, $U = 869$, $z = -2.42$, $p = 0.015$, $r = -0.24$), which is considered harder by women than by men.

Task selection

The tasks that were done by less than 75% of the female participants were trimming hedges, mowing

the lawn, moving heavy objects, lawn edging and pruning trees (Figure 3, left side). Follow-up questions (Figure 3, right side) explored the reasons behind why people do not undertake certain tasks and show that 'Someone else does it' was the most frequently selected reason for not doing an activity for those who had the relevant feature in their garden. According to another question ($N = 89$, female) the most frequent delegate was the spouse/partner (45%), followed by a paid gardener (10%).

Effect of gender

Pearson's chi-squared tests revealed it was more likely for males than for females over 50 to do the following tasks: mowing the lawn ($X^2(1) = 11.46$, $p = .001$, odds ratio (OR) = 3.5), , trimming hedges ($X^2(1) = 5.09$, $p = .024$, OR = 2.2), and moving heavy objects ($X^2(1) = 17.32$, $p < .001$, OR = 5.4). In contrast, for pruning plants ($X^2(1) = 3.975$, $p = .046$, OR = 7.1), females were more likely to complete the task.

Table 2. Perception of how hard a task is on a VAS of 0-100 for females over 50. Respondent numbers vary based on the gardening tasks they had previously selected they do.

Difficulty of a task (0-100)			
Task	N	Median	Range
Moving heavy objects in the garden	42	54	100
Trimming hedges	28	35	95
Pruning trees	64	30	100
Loosening the soil	78	18	100
Gathering leaves and cuttings	79	8	100
Lawn edging	59	7	100
Pruning plants	87	6	100
Mowing the lawn	39	6	100
Watering	86	5	100
Weeding	88	3	100
Planting	87	2	100
Sowing seeds	77	0	100

Table 3. Enjoyment of task on a VAS of 0-100 for females over 50. Respondent numbers vary based on the gardening tasks they had previously selected they do.

Enjoyment of a task (0-100)			
Task	N	Median	Range
Planting	87	94	97
Sowing seeds	77	79	93
Pruning plants	87	67	100
Pruning trees	64	55	99
Weeding	88	54	100
Loosening the soil	78	47	100
Watering	86	47	100
Trimming hedges	28	42	77
Mowing the lawn	39	42	100
Lawn edging	59	39	100
Gathering leaves and cuttings	79	36	100
Moving heavy objects in the garden	42	12	88

Figure 3. Percentage of female participants over 50 that do each gardening task (out of total N=88) and reasons why participants do not do a task for the five least done tasks. Participants were allowed to select multiple reasons and the percentages represent the percentages of total reasons given.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore the gardening experiences of older women to establish the potential for improvement of this experience so that participation in the healthy gardening activities can be increased. The survey-based study sought to explore reasons people have for gardening, the perceived importance of tools in influencing motivation to do gardening activities and differences between which gardening tasks are done and how these tasks are perceived.

The group of female participants is intrinsically motivated to do gardening with the most important reasons relating to how the garden makes them feel, the result obtained and the connection to nature, with males over 50 giving lower overall scores. These results reflect the passion of older women for this leisure activity. They align with market research that found women have more interest in gardening and enjoy it more than men (The Horticultural Trades Association, 2011). Gardening is a source of happiness that provides older women with both mental and physical wellbeing. As such, they do not need to be pushed to the activities, but it is instead imperative to remove any barriers in their current experience to enable them to continue to do the activities.

Tool aspects were found to be an important influence to participants' motivation to do gardening activities, especially the suitability, ease of use and weight of the tool as well as comfort of the tool handle. If these tool aspects are not optimal in the perception of the older women, these results imply that this might negatively impact their motivation to do the activities. In turn, improving these tool aspects could help to improve the overall gardening experience of older women.

The most common reason for older women not to do tasks was that 'someone else does it' and it was found that this other person is usually their spouse/partner.

However, the reality is that access to this or other outside help can become more limited with age; getting older is associated with increased risk of exclusion from social relationships (Barnes, Blom, Cox, Lessof, & Walker, 2006). To allow women to continue to do gardening, they should therefore be able to work independently.

Nicklet, Anderson, & Yen (2014) suggest that older adults have not been involved in development of gardening activities so far and their input might aid in creating interventions with higher engagement and retention. Moving heavy things in the garden was found to be one of the tasks with lowest participation rates and highest perceived difficulty, whilst also being the least enjoyed. This is a task that has a supporting role to many of the gardening activities. Through co-design with the target group of older women, the task of moving heavy things in the garden will serve as a case study and will be investigated further in future work through which new products will be developed. By focusing on improving this task through tool design it is expected that a positive impact can be made on the gardening experience of older women. This could increase their potential to participate independently in the healthy gardening activities.

Conclusion

The aim of this survey-based study was to explore the gardening experiences of older women. Participating in gardening activities has both health and wellbeing benefits. The older women featured in this study are intrinsically motivated to do gardening. However, the results point for a need to support them with the tasks that have low participation rates and that are considered difficult and not enjoyable. Moving heavy things in the garden was found to be the most difficult, least enjoyable and one of the tasks the least amount of participants did. Tool aspects were found to be an important influence on whether these women are motivated to do gardening activities. When tasks that are difficult and not enjoyable are improved through tool design, it is likely that fewer older women will be dependent upon others to help them with gardening, thus promoting independence and improving the gardening experience of these older women so that participation in the healthy gardening activities can be increased.

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